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“BATTLE CRY OF AN EDUCATOR”

Ignite the Passion, the purpose to keep the fire burning
Deliver excellence and keep believing
The mission to fulfill and share one's blessing
It makes sense to keep molding and its worth remembering

The power of learning just keep it roaring
To serve as guide and pathway just keep it soaring
It is a fulfillment and really uplifting
To keep the mind learning and growing

A mission fulfilled, a sense of growth
It is a true sense of strength and hope
To light a candle and pass it on
To a brighter road towards sustainable and development goals

Growing together, enriching lives
“Better Together”, a Battle Cry
Collaboration and insights, a sense of belonging
Let us hold each other's hand for a Better Philippines